

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Review Article

**AMYOTROPHIC LATERAL SCLEROSIS (ALS), REVIEW OF
EFFECTIVE SCREENING AND THERAPEUTIC OPTIONS**

¹Kawthar Saeed al Sultan, ²Abdulaziz Ayad ALanazi, ³Eiman Muhammad Alnemer, ⁴Hussain Saeed Al Sultan, ⁵Afaf Meshal Almjlad, ⁶Abdurhman Aiash Alrwaili, ⁷Wasan lafi Alanazi, ⁸Abdulmajeed Haddaj Alruwaily, ⁹Malak Ibrahim Alanazi, ¹⁰Maryam Saeed Alanazi

Abstract:

Improving the understanding of ALS pathogenesis is crucial in developing earlier diagnostic approaches in addition to proposing new effective treatments. Thus, this review will provide the most recent research studies related to pathogenesis, diagnostic examinations, and treatments. We performed a computerized search using electronic databases; MEDLINE, EMBASE, and google scholar, through November, 2017. Search strategies used following MeSH terms in searching via these databases: "Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis", "diagnosis", "screening", "management", "therapy". Unfortunately, ALS is considered an incurable disease, with an anticipated life expectancy of 3- 5 years after the onset of symptoms. Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis is a devastating neurodegenerative problem that typically begins with focal muscle weakness and ultimately progresses to death from respiratory failing. Although there is no cure for ALS, therapy could enhance both the quality and length of life. Care of ALS patients is best given by multidisciplinary ALS centers along with family physicians. It is important to continue nutritional research studies in order to give better care to ALS patients, as some evidence has shown they could help to alleviate the effect of the disease on their daily lives. Present discoveries of the underlying mechanism of ALS have helped to reduce the progression of the illness. Thus, the future treatments need to aim toward preventing neuronal damage, as patients progress from their initial start.

Corresponding author:**Kawthar Saeed al Sultan.**

QR code

Please cite this article in press Kawthar Saeed al Sultan et al., *Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis (ALS), Review Of Effective Screening And Therapeutic Options.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(01).

INTRODUCTION:

Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS) is a fatal motor neuron problem that is, identified by progressive loss of the upper and lower motor neurons (LMNs) at the spine or bulbar degree [1].

ALS was initially defined in 1869 by French neurologist Jean-Martin Charcot [1] [2]. The illness became popular in the United States when baseball player Lou Gehrig was detected with the illness in 1939 [3]. ALS is additionally referred to as Charcot disease in honor of the first individual to explain the disease, Jean-Martin Charcot, and motor neuron disease (MND) as it is just one of the 5 MNDs that affect motor neurons. There are 4 various other well-known MNDs: Primary lateral sclerosis (PLS), progressive muscular atrophy (PMA), progressive bulbar palsy (PBP), and pseudobulbar palsy [1], [3].

ALS is categorized in 2 types. One of the most common kind is sporadic (90- 95%) which has no obvious genetically inherited element. The remaining 5- 10% of the instances are familial-type ALS (FALS) as a result of their associated genetic dominant inheritance element [4]. The first start of signs and symptoms is generally in between the ages of 50 and 65 [5]. The most common symptoms that appear in both sorts of ALS are muscle weakness, twitching, and cramping, which ultimately can lead to the problems of muscles [6]. In the most advanced stages, ALS patients will certainly develop symptoms of dyspnea and dysphagia [7].

Improving the understanding of ALS pathogenesis is crucial in developing earlier diagnostic approaches in addition to proposing new effective treatments. Thus, this review will provide the most recent research studies related to pathogenesis, diagnostic examinations, and treatments.

METHODOLOGY:

We performed a computerized search using electronic databases; MEDLINE, EMBASE, and google scholar, through November, 2017. Search strategies used following MeSH terms in searching via these databases: "Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis", "diagnosis", "screening", "management", "therapy". Then we also searched the bibliographies of included studies for further relevant references to our review. Restriction to only English published study with human subject.

DISCUSSION:

- **Pathogenesis**

Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis is generally classified as a solitary condition entity, but proof recommends

that it is a clinical syndrome arising from several possible reasons [8]. It is most likely that sporadic cases of ALS are multifactorial and pertaining to several environmental factors and a genetic predisposition. Epidemiologic research studies, however, have not had the ability to identify any certain causative factors. Smoking is the only possible risk element recognized so far. Unproven risk elements consist of ingestion of lead or agricultural chemicals, physical prowess (quality in athletics), and intake of nutritional glutamate [9], [10]. A causative retrovirus has been considered, yet is not yet sustained by evidence.

Between 5% and 10% of cases of ALS follow a domestic inheritance. Many causative gene anomalies have been identified, of which superoxide dismutase 1 (SOD1) is the most common [8]. Researchers have normally utilized mice with SOD1 mutations to try to decipher the pathogenesis of ALS. This research study has identified numerous factors involved in pathogenesis, consisting of protein aggregation, glutamate excitotoxicity, oxidative injury, swelling, mitochondrial disorder in motor neurons, and defective axonal transport [9], [10].

- **Diagnosis**

Without a diagnostic test for ALS, clinicians primarily depend on recognizing the combination of UMN and LMN signs in the same body region, with subsequent evidence of condition development to various other regions. The El Escorial requirements [11] revised in 1997 [12], utilize a mix of UMN and LMN indications to establish levels of diagnostic certainty. Clinical test investigators have tended to enrol patients with either probable or certain ALS according to the El Escorial criteria, highlighting their universality, although incorporation of these analysis features as enrolment requirements may be argued as limiting [13]. Furthermore, these requirements could have poor sensitivity, particularly in the early stages of ALS when patients are more than likely to benefit from therapeutic intervention [14]. Because of these criticisms, the requirements have been changed to assist early diagnosis [15] and to optimise levels of diagnostic assurance, essential in the medical trial establishing [16].

There is commonly a long delay prior to a definitive diagnosis is gotten to, partially due to the insidious beginning of symptoms, with the median time to diagnosis of about 14 months [17]. Uncommon clinical performances, a low index of suspicion, and misinterpretation of neurophysiological or neuroradiological results are common causes of diagnostic unpredictability. However, diagnostic delay can bring about use unsuitable therapies, a

hold-up in starting appropriate pharmacological and symptomatic therapies, and issues in managing psychosocial variables.

The medical diagnosis of ALS is devastating for the patient and relative, and have to be managed sensitively. Patients and family members could bring the emotional concern of an insensitively provided diagnosis for the entire illness program, and initial indecision about the diagnosis in irregular cases could delay the procedure of approving the terminal prognosis of the illness. Scheduling a follow-up appointment soon after diagnosis is beneficial to answer concerns not managed throughout the first consultation and could help provide further information regarding support networks, which are

well developed in the majority of created countries [18].

Although unusual, the presence of numerous disorders that imitate ALS requires an extensive diagnostic assessment, which usually consists of structural imaging and neurophysiological and laboratory investigations, to reduce the possibility of an inaccurate diagnosis (table1). In instances of pure LMN syndromes, genetic testing for Kennedy's illness, an X-linked bulbospinal atrophy, and spine muscular atrophy is necessary [19].Muscle mass biopsy examples can be of more analysis worth for omitting uncommon myopathies such as polyglucosan body condition or for confirming the presence of ALS by suggesting atrophy of mixed-fibre types.

Table1. Differential diagnosis of ALS and appropriate investigations

<p>Disorders of motor neurons</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Spinal muscular atrophy (SMN gene deletion assay) •X-linked spinobulbar muscular atrophy (Kennedy's disease; increased CAG repeats in DNA from blood) •Poliomyelitis or post-polio syndrome (history, NCS, electromyography) •Hexosaminidase A deficiency (white-cell enzyme testing) 	<p>Disorders of motor nerves</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Multifocal motor neuropathy (NCS, electromyography, ganglioside GM1 antibodies) •Chronic inflammatory demyelinating neuropathy (NCS, lumbar puncture) •Cramp-fasciculation syndrome (NCS, electromyography) •Neuromyotonia (antibodies to voltage-gated potassium channels) •Hereditary spastic paraparesis plus (gene mutation testing) •Hereditary motor neuropathy with pyramidal features
<p>Structural CNS and spinal lesions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Syringomyelia or syringobulbia (MRI) •Tabes dorsalis (syphilis serology) •Multiple sclerosis (MRI, oligoclonal bands, evoked responses) •Monomelic spinal muscular atrophy (Hirayama's disease; electromyography, MRI) •Lyme disease (Lyme serology) •Human T-lymphotropic virus-1 (HIV) 	<p>Myopathy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Inclusion body myositis (electromyography, CK, muscle biopsy sample) •Polymyositis (electromyography, CK, muscle biopsy sample, autoimmune screens) •Dermatomyositis (electromyography, CK, skin, and muscle biopsy sample) •Polyglucosan body disease (NCS, electromyography, muscle or nerve biopsy sample)
<p>Endocrine</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Thyrotoxicosis (thyroid function tests, electromyography, muscle biopsy sample) •Hyperparathyroidism (calcium ion and parathyroid testing) •Subacute combined degeneration (vitamin B12 concentrations) •Coeliac disease (serum testing, bowel biopsy sample) 	<p>Disorders of neuromuscular junction</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Myasthenia gravis (acetylcholine receptor antibodies, MuSK antibodies, repetitive stimulation, single-fibre electromyography) •Lambert-Eaton myasthenic syndrome (repetitive stimulation)

ALS=amyotrophic lateral sclerosis. CK=creatine kinase. NCS=nerve conduction studies. MuSK=muscle-specific tyrosine kinase.

Regular neurophysiological examinations of patients with ALS consist of nerve conduction studies, electromyography, and, less generally, transcranial magnetic excitement. Nerve conduction research studies are vital to omit disorders that mimic ALS, especially demyelinating motor neuropathies [20]. Motor nerve transmission is normal in the beginning of ALS, but in advanced illness the compound muscle activity prospective amplitude becomes decreased, showing denervation [21]. Sensory nerve transmission is typically normal in patients with ALS, distinguishing ALS from demyelinating neuropathies. Popular abnormalities of sensory nerve conduction studies should raise suspicion of an alternative diagnosis. In patients presenting with predominantly LMN searchings for, treatable conditions such as multifocal electric motor neuropathy must be thought about, with indication of conduction block in a minimum of two motor nerves outside the usual entrapment sites.

Motor systems that make it through can terminate spontaneously as fasciculation potentials, clinically noticeable as spontaneous muscle twitching- a regular attribute of ALS [23]. When identified in the tongue, fasciculations are extremely specific for ALS. The presence of fasciculations in the lack of other electromyographical findings should be interpreted with care and can be an indication of less serious disorders, specifically "benign" cramp-fasciculation disorder. On the other hand, just recently modified consensus guidelines (known as the Awaji Island standards) have recommended that fasciculations need to be believed to amount fibrillation possibilities in individuals with clinically suspected ALS [22]. Additionally, fasciculations in ALS are intricate ("malignant"), indicating re-innervation, and have diagnostic significance when combined with chronic neurogenic changes.

• Treatment

Treatment is palliative and several individuals benefit from care by a multidisciplinary group including: a neurologist, particularly trained nurses, pulmonologist, speech therapist, physical therapist, occupational therapist, respiratory specialist, nutritionist, psycho therapist, social worker, and genetic counselor.

Data suggest that people under the care of such a group might have a much better prognosis [23]. The factors affecting survival consist of: age, essential capability, tiredness, body strength, spasticity,

household income, and depression [25], most of which can be managed by the appropriate professional in the multidisciplinary group.

Riluzole is the only currently FDA-approved medication for the therapy of ALS. Its system of activity is believed to be glutamate inhibition. Clinical trials have revealed marginal slowing down of illness development in some but not all people. Riluzole is associated with elevation of serum alanine aminotransferase degrees in 10% to 15% of treated people; in unusual cases it may cause bone marrow anxiety [26].

Oral secretions in people with bulbar signs can be reduced with tricyclic antidepressants and anticholinergic agents, thus reducing the requirement for sucking.

Pseudobulbar affect can be handled with antidepressants such as Nuedexta[®] (dextromethophan and quinidine).

Swallowing difficulties can be alleviated by thickening liquids and pureeing solid food, as well as eventually using a gastrostomy tube to assist maintain calorie consumption and hydration. Nutritional management, a prognostic factor for survival, has ended up being an emphasis in the clinical setup.

Medications such as baclofen and benzodiazepines could aid relieve spasticity and muscle cramps; nevertheless, weakness and lethargy are common side effects. Individualized moderate-intensity endurance-type exercises for the trunk and limbs could assist to reduce spasticity.

Low-tech (e.g., alphabet board) and high-tech (i.e., computer-assisted) devices could assist speech and communication. The current development of the eye movement-controlled on-screen keyboard might enable interaction for people without any remaining arm or leg function.

Assistive tools, such as walkers or wheelchairs, can aid mobility; and others, such as bathroom installations, health center bed, and Hoyer lift, could assist in tasks of everyday living in your home.

Ventilatory assistance might consist of use bilevel positive airway pressure (BIPAP), which has played an increasing function in preserving and extending

quality of life in persons with ALS. In 1999, the American Academy of Neurology published norms recommending the initiation of noninvasive ventilation (NIV) in people with a theoretic forced vital capacity (FVC) less than 50% of anticipated [27]. Studies reveal that mean survival substantially raises when NIV is launched prior to the beginning of bulbar signs and symptoms. Therefore, examination by a pulmonologist need to be taken on before decrease of the forced vital capacity listed below 50%.

Although tracheostomy and ventilatory support could extend lifetime, affected individuals usually decrease these treatments [28].

The tremendous psychological and social impact of ALS on both influenced people and caregivers has to be continually dealt with [29]. Hospice care, typically set up when FVC is less than 30%, contributes to the person's convenience in the terminal stages.

Table2. Symptomatic care in ALS

<p>Weakness and disability</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Orthotics (eg, ankle foot orthosis, neck collars) •Physiotherapy •Adaptive aids (eg, walking frame, wheelchair) 	<p>Dysphagia</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Assessment by speech therapist and dietitian •Safe swallowing techniques and modified diet •Insertion of gastrostomy tube
<p>Dyspnoea and poor cough</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Ventilatory support •Morphine or benzodiazepines •Chest physiotherapy •Suction machine •Manually assisted coughing techniques 	<p>Pain (ie, musculoskeletal pain and cramps, fasciculations and spasticity, skin pressure pain caused by immobility)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Physiotherapy, NSAIDs •Muscle relaxants (baclofen, botulinum toxin) •Anticonvulsants (eg, gabapentin) •Re-positioning and pressure area care •Opioid drugs •Pressure-relieving cushions and mattress
<p>Dysarthria</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Assessment by speech pathologist •Communication aids •Educate family and caregivers 	<p>Thickened saliva</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Natural remedies (eg, papaya) •Ensure adequate hydration •Saline nebulisers; nebulised N-acetylcysteine •Suctioning of the mouth •Mouth care
<p>Sialorrhoea</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Anticholinergic antidepressants (eg, amitriptyline) •Anticholinergic drugs (eg, glycopyrronium bromide) •Botulinum toxin injections •Radiation of salivary glands •Mouth-care products •Suction 	<p>Emotional lability</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Educate patients with ALS and caregivers •Amitriptyline •Benzodiazepines •Dextromethorphan hydrobromide/quinidine sulfate
<p>Depression and anxiety</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Counselling •Benzodiazepines •Antidepressants 	<p>Constipation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Dietary changes (eg, increase fluid and fibre intake) •Use formulations high in bran, bulk, or fibre •Regular oral aperients (Movicol [Norgine, the Netherlands] or suppositories).
<p>Sleep disturbance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Treat underlying problem •Respiratory review, non-invasive ventilation •Benzodiazepines, tricyclic antidepressants 	<p>Cognitive changes (frontal lobe dysfunction or dementia)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Explain symptomatology to caregivers and family •Antidepressant therapies

ALS=amyotrophic lateral sclerosis. Data from Andersen and colleagues [30] and Miller and colleagues[31].

CONCLUSION:

Unfortunately, ALS is considered an incurable disease, with an anticipated life expectancy of 3- 5

years after the onset of symptoms. Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis is a devastating neurodegenerative problem that typically begins with focal muscle

weakness and ultimately progresses to death from respiratory failing. Although there is no cure for ALS, therapy could enhance both the quality and length of life. Care of ALS patients is best given by multidisciplinary ALS centers along with family physicians. It is important to continue nutritional research studies in order to give better care to ALS patients, as some evidence has shown they could help to alleviate the effect of the disease on their daily lives. Present discoveries of the underlying mechanism of ALS have helped to reduce the progression of the illness. Thus, the future treatments need to aim toward preventing neuronal damage, as patients progress from their initial start.

REFERENCE:

1. Rowland LP, Shneider NA. Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis. *N Engl J Med*. 2001;344:1688–700.
2. Talbot K. Motor neurone disease. *Postgrad Med J*. 2002;78:513–9.
3. Leigh PN, Ray-Chaudhuri K. Motor neuron disease. *J Neurol Neurosurg Psychiatry*. 1994;57:886–96.
4. Ticozzi N, Vance C, Leclerc AL, Keagle P, Glass JD, McKenna-Yasek D, et al. Mutational analysis reveals the FUS homolog TAF15 as a candidate gene for familial amyotrophic lateral sclerosis. *Am J Med Genet B Neuropsychiatr Genet*. 2011;156B:285–90.
5. Logroscino G, Traynor BJ, Hardiman O, Chiò A, Mitchell D, Swingler RJ, et al. Incidence of amyotrophic lateral sclerosis in Europe. *J Neurol Neurosurg Psychiatry*. 2010;81:385–90.
6. Goetz CG. Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis: Early contributions of Jean-Martin Charcot. *Muscle Nerve*. 2000;23:336–43.
7. Leigh PN, Abrahams S, Al-Chalabi A, Ampong MA, Goldstein LH, Johnson J, et al. The management of motor neurone disease. *J Neurol Neurosurg Psychiatry*. 2003;74(Suppl 4):iv32–iv47.
8. Strong MJ, Kesavapany S, Pant HC. The pathobiology of amyotrophic lateral sclerosis: a proteinopathy? *J Neuropathol Exp Neurol*. 2005;64(8):649–664.
9. Armon C. Epidemiology of amyotrophic lateral sclerosis/motor neuron disease. In: Shaw PJ, Strong MJ, editors. *Motor neuron disorders*. Philadelphia, Pa: Butterworth Heinemann; 2003. pp. 167–205.
10. Belli S, Vanacore N. Proportionate mortality of Italian soccer players: is amyotrophic lateral sclerosis an occupational disease? *Eur J Epidemiol*. 2005;20(3):237–242.
11. Brooks, BR. El Escorial World Federation of Neurology criteria for the diagnosis of

- amyotrophic lateral sclerosis. Subcommittee on Motor Neuron Diseases/Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis of the World Federation of Neurology Research Group on Neuromuscular Diseases and the El Escorial “Clinical limits of amyotrophic lateral sclerosis” workshop contributors. *J Neurol Sci*. 1994; 124: 96–107.
12. Miller, RG, Munsat, TL, Swash, M, and Brooks, BR. Consensus guidelines for the design and implementation of clinical trials in ALS. World Federation of Neurology committee on Research. *J Neurol Sci*. 1999; 169: 2–12
13. Kiernan, MC. Motor neuron disease: a Pandora's box. *MJA*. 2003; 178: 311–312
14. Traynor, BJ, Codd, MB, Corr, B, Forde, C, and Frost, E. Hardiman O. Clinical features of Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis according to the El Escorial and Airlie House Diagnostic Criteria. *Arch Neurol*. 2000; 57: 1171–1176
15. Ross, MA, Miller, RG, Berchert, L et al. Toward earlier diagnosis of amyotrophic lateral sclerosis: revised criteria. rhCNTF ALS Study Group. *Neurology*. 1998; 50: 768–772
16. Beghi, E, Balzarini, C, Bogliun, G et al. Reliability of the El Escorial diagnostic criteria for amyotrophic lateral sclerosis. *Neuroepidemiology*. 2002; 21: 265–270
17. Chio, A. ISIS Survey: an international study on the diagnostic process and its implications in amyotrophic lateral sclerosis. *J Neurol*. 1999; 246: III1–III5
18. Andersen, PM, Borasio, GD, Dengler, R et al. Good practice in the management of amyotrophic lateral sclerosis: clinical guidelines. An evidence-based review with good practice points. EALSC Working Group. *Amyotroph Lateral Scler*. 2007; 8: 195–213
19. Rocha, JA, Reis, C, Simoes, F, Fonseca, J, and Mendes Ribeiro, J. Diagnostic investigation and multidisciplinary management in motor neuron disease. *J Neurol*. 2005; 252: 1435–1447
20. Eisen, A and Swash, M. Clinical neurophysiology of ALS. *Clin Neurophysiol*. 2001; 112: 2190–2201.
21. Daube, JR. Electrodiagnostic studies in amyotrophic lateral sclerosis and other motor neuron disorders. *Muscle Nerve*. 2000; 23: 1488–1502.
22. de Carvalho, M, Dengler, R, Eisen, A et al. Electrodiagnostic criteria for diagnosis of ALS. *Clin Neurophysiol*. 2008; 119: 497–503
23. Gubbay, SS, Kahana, E, Zilber, N, Cooper, G, Pintov, S, and Leibowitz, Y. Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis. A study of its presentation and prognosis. *J Neurol*. 1985; 232: 295–300
24. van den Berg JP, de Groot IJ, Joha BC, van

- Haelst JM, van Gorcom P, Kalmijn S. Development and implementation of the Dutch protocol for rehabilitative management in amyotrophic lateral sclerosis. *Amyotroph Lateral Scler Other Motor Neuron Disord*. 2004;5:226–9.
25. Paillisse C, Lacomblez L, Dib M, Bensimon G, Garcia-Acosta S, Meininger V. Prognostic factors for survival in amyotrophic lateral sclerosis patients treated with riluzole. *Amyotroph Lateral Scler Other Motor Neuron Disord*. 2005;6:37–44.
 26. Bensimon G, Doble A. The tolerability of riluzole in the treatment of patients with amyotrophic lateral sclerosis. *Expert Opin Drug Saf*. 2004;3:525–34.
 27. Miller RG, Mitchell JD, Lyon M, Moore DH. Riluzole for amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS)/motor neuron disease (MND). *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. 2002. CD001447.
 28. Albert SM, Murphy PL, Del Bene ML, Rowland LP. A prospective study of preferences and actual treatment choices in ALS. *Neurology*. 1999;53:278–83.
 29. Goldstein LH, Adamson M, Jeffrey L, Down K, Barby T, Wilson C, Leigh PN. The psychological impact of MND on patients and carers. *J Neurol Sci*. 1998;160 Suppl 1:S114–21.
 30. Andersen, PM, Borasio, GD, Dengler, R et al. Good practice in the management of amyotrophic lateral sclerosis: clinical guidelines. An evidence-based review with good practice points. EALSC Working Group. *Amyotroph Lateral Scler*. 2007; 8: 195–213.
 31. Miller, RG, Jackson, CE, Kasarskis, EJ et al. Practice parameter update: the care of the patient with amyotrophic lateral sclerosis: multidisciplinary care, symptom management, and cognitive/behavioral impairment (an evidence-based review): report of the Quality Standards Subcommittee of the American Academy of Neurology. *Neurology*. 2009; 73: 1227–1233.